

Social Media and Democracy: Facebook as a Tool for the Establishment of Democracy in Pakistan

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Abstract

This study investigates and describes the utilization of one of the Social Media's platform Facebook, which is a helpful tool for the establishment of democracy with in a state and political involvement in the general election of Pakistan. The study examines the opinions and political efficacy of the Facebook members and groups whose discourses about the democracy and general election system of Pakistan are becoming popular. The topic was chosen as the relevance of the establishment of democracy and political participation to Facebook opinions and discussions about Pakistani democracy and political participation among the Pakistani people of different age groups, gender and qualification. The thesis consists of mixed methods, applying both quantitative and qualitative. The sample size is 247 out of population 455. The instrument as questionnaires was measure of opinions of the respondents. Hypotheses were tested and found positive as the findings of this learning. This finding would contribute to determine the positive role of social medial platform Facebook role in the establishment of democracy and political participation in Pakistan.

Keywords: Democracy, Political efficacy, social media, Facebook, Pakistan, Political Participation, Political Parties, Pakistani Politicians.

1. Introduction

In the last decades of 20th Century internet stood familiar among common men, and now it has penetrated in almost all societies of the world. It has proved itself to be a very useful innovation in multiple ways. The most important entity that came into creation by means of cyberspace to community is social media. Social Media has created modern means for people's communication. Usage of social media these days, is not only conserved for discussion of family events but also utilized for sharing of photographs and videos, moreover, it can actually create a history and make differences in actual world. Pondering not many platforms of Social media, for example, Facebook and Twitter. Facebook is by all accounts most unmistakable nowadays and is a noteworthy foundation of Social Media, the site was made by understudy of Harvard, Mark Zuckerberg in 2004 as a stage where loved ones get associated. First and foremost, it was applied by secondary school and afterward understudies, later in 2012 Facebook developed and earned 845 million dynamic clients all around. The utilization of Social Media developed by practically 56% of purchasers having multi-profiles in 2016 to the normal customer referring to utilization of in excess of four diverse Social Media stages in 2018 (Duggan & Page, 2016; Smith & Anders & Caiazza, 2018). According to Flew (2002), the standard of communication has modified from traditional means that ensures the communication by means of Telephone, Letters and Newspaper; to innovative media which includes, social networking sites and mobile phones. Specifically,

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eating up news from standard resources, like papers, TV, radio and the net, is determinedly associated with polishing off casting a poll (Gainous & Wagner, 2014; Smets & van Ham, 2013).

It is the way wherein people choose out representatives, display ends on key issues, and in specific spots certainly make law via the use of techniques for the motion technique. The scholars like Gottfried, Barthel, Shearer, & Mitchell (2016) elaborate that with the development of the net, and starting past due net based totally systems management like twitter and Facebook, men have progressively, got information and political records in another manner.

A wide range of politicians are also the active users of different on social websites to utilize the online platform to make their presence strong on Twitter and Facebook. Constructing their official pages and profiles on the above sites, Politicians often share their recent activities, their posture on different matters, and also inspire people to share their ideologies. In such manner, they remain active and alive in front of their followers (Bjornlund, 2005). The politicians' narratives, data, software, and news events can reinterpret a politician's win or failure about the role that misinformation and disinformation play in his or her election. The relationship of democracy and the media in Pakistan have always remained under complex. In true means, Pakistan has never seen a true democratic government since its inception because the media organizations and their providers (Journalists), are conventionally or non-conventionally threatened by both state and non-state performers.

1.2 Scope of the Study

This research study will prove helpful to all the political stakeholders and the Pakistani youth, who want to take active part in the political activities and democratic process of Pakistan on the basis of the recommendations to be carefully derived from the findings of this study.

1.3 Purpose of the Research

The reason for the query is to search the character of Facebook social media that Facebook contributes in establishing political efficacy and democracy in Pakistan. Through research and explores it is planned to be searching out if web-based life can give political activists additional opportunity and movement limit than predominant press in Pakistan's political conjuncture.

1.4 Statement of the Problem

The political activists of Pakistan have intricacies to enact their political motives and compare with the watchers and their potential supporters through social media. The issue emerges from the character of Facebook in social media as to what Facebook contributes in establishing political efficacy and democracy in Pakistan.

1.5 Objectives of the study

1. To examine the utilization of Modern Media as a helpful instrument for the establishment of democracy in Pakistan.
2. To examine use of Facebook on political involvement in the election processes of Pakistan.

1.6 Research Questions of Study

The Research Questions addresses that how the online networking is being used and might be needed to make political mindfulness and developments in Pakistan. The research questions are as follow:

1. Is the Social Media consumption a helpful device for the establishment of democratic state in Pakistan?
2. Is it possible that use of social media platform Facebook may help on political contribution in the general elections of Pakistan?

1.7 Hypotheses of the Study

H1: Usage of social media has a prominent and optimistic impact over politics in Pakistan.

H2: Use of Facebook has a substantial and constructive impact on the democratic mindset of the people of Pakistan.

2. Review of Literature

There are numerous Social Networking Sites which support a wide range of benefits and practices technologically. The main high-tech structures are dependable and the values that appear around SNSs are in diverse forms. Some experts like Boyd and Ellison (2007) defined social Media as, “the Websites which allows profile creation and visibility of relationships between users”.

Zargar (2018) likewise characterized it as "an online stage which individuals use to make informal organizations or carefully social relations with others, who share individual, profession interests, activities, and genuine correspondence". In today's world Social Media is an ever-present aspect of life that encompasses us. Pretty much every promotion, regardless of whether TV, radio, magazine, film review, digital recording, paper, or somewhere else, will make reference to its web-based social networking nearness somehow or another. Rogers (2019) clarified that one can like others on Facebook, look at others on Instagram, or maybe watch ones' channel on YouTube are only a portion of the snares that organizations will give to additionally assemble their image and increment their perceivability.

Korta (1995) referenced that the advanced gadget were moreover used to have mental effects in the American people. The believable assurance effects of these activities consolidate dealing the commitment of data; planting disunity and vulnerability in the American open about the authenticity of information arrange reports, and inciting requests concerning the ubiquity-based strategy itself.

3. Research Methodology

3.1 Geographical Distribution of the Sample

The current study focuses on one of the social media platforms Facebook to be an essential instrument for the creation of democracy and political participation in Pakistan. As appears, this study is conducted within the purview of Pakistan. Our focus is the online Facebook opinions and communication responses on the democratic system and political participation by the Pakistani respondents who have access and have their accounts on Facebook.

3.2 Demographic Distribution of the Sample

This section of the research covers the characteristics of the demographic distribution of the sample. Total population on the Facebook accounts was 455.

3.3 Sample by gender

In the following Table 1, gender-wise sample size has been shown with percentage of each gender.

Table 1: Distribution of the respondents according to the gender (N= 247).

S. No.	Gender	Number of Respondents	Percentage
1	Males	128	51.8%
2	Females	119	48.2%
	Total	247	100%

3.4 Samples by Age Group

According in conformity with the youth about the respondents the pattern was once distributed namely acknowledged among the consequent table 2

Table 2: Distribution of the respondents according to their age group (N= 247)

S. No.	Age Group	Number of Respondents	Percentage
1	18- 25 years	120	48.6%
2	26- 35 years	99	40.1%
3	36- 45 years	28	11.3%
4	45 years and above	---	---
	Total	247	100%

3.5 Population, Sample and Sampling Technique

3.5.1 Population

It is an assortment of all elements one is learning and drawing conclusions (Levin & Rubin, 1997). Total Facebook users which are added in the group of the researcher are the population of this study. The questionnaire was uploaded on the Facebook and responses were collected online. In this current study our total population on the Facebook accounts was 455.

3.5.2 Sample and Sampling Technique

A sample is collection of few elements of the population. (Levin & Rubin, 1997). In this study, the sample size is 247 out of population 455, who were comprised of Face Book individual members.

3.5.3 Sampling Technique

Sampling is a statistical technique to accumulate information about a population. The values over the population features are concise by way of assured numerical descriptive measures, recognised as like parameters. The values regarding the populace parameters estimate the observations to calculate an analogous numerical measure recognised as facts (Chaudhry, 1995).

3.6 Description of Instrument

An estimation instrument suggests a source which an expert uses to accumulate and record the fundamental data and subsequently convert into quantitative structure for his assessment. In the human sciences prepares the consistently used instruments for evaluating the components are studies, (Muhammad, 1985, p. 177-182, cited in Channar, 2010).

3.6.1 Questionnaire

A questionnaire is a typical and famous information assortment instrument to be utilized in overview. Every respondent is required to react to a similar arrangement of inquiries. It is an effective strategy to gather reactions from tests preceding quantitative information examination. Surveys are broadly utilized for expressive or informative exploration (Saunders, Lewis, & Thornhill, 2012). Polls with normalized questions are accepted to be surely known a similar route by all respondents (Saunders et al, 2012).

3.6.2 Layout of the Questionnaire

The questionnaire was partitioned into three pieces of this examination study. Initial segment of the survey secured the segment profile of respondents. The segment data comprises of sex, age gathering, and level of instruction. Second piece of the survey was identified with the utilization of web and online networking. Third part is about internet-based life and legislative issues.

Table 3: Layout of the questionnaire (Part 1)

Part	Demographic profile	No of items
One	Gender Age group Level of Education	3

Table 4: Layout of the questionnaire (Part 2)

Part	Variable	No of questions
Two	Usage of internet and social media	6
Three	Social Media and Politics	10

3.6.3 Scales of Measurement

Sizes of estimation suggest the gadgets which are used for assessing attributes in the instruments used in research (Channar, 2010). Sizes of estimation are assigned apparent, ordinal, stretch, and extent scales. In this investigation apparent, range, and ordinal scales have been used. An ostensible scale is utilized to gauge sex, age gathering, and level of training. A stretch scale is utilized to quantify age gathering of the respondents while ostensible and ordinal scales are utilized to gauge perspectives/inclinations of the respondents with respect to the utilization of the web and the online life. These are likewise used to quantify the job of online life in governmental issues.

3.7 Data Analysis

Data present out of the respondents through metering poll have been arranged by Statistical Package of Social Sciences statistic files. The SPSS model 22 is utilized for all measurable investigation into this research.

3.7.1 Data analysing techniques

Statistics examining the methods speak in accordance with every statistical technique concurrently analyse more than one measurement of each single than goal beneath management (Hair, Anderson, Tatham, & William, 1995). The statistical metering tools chronic of that lookup comprised on descriptive statistics, correlation or regression.

3.7.2 Descriptive Statistics

In accordance with Zikmund, Babin, Carr, & Griffin (2012), picturesque evaluation refers to transform a form on the rough statistics to understand or interpret. The demographic plan (gender, youth, team, education) of respondents are examined and presented by use of descriptive statistics.

3.7.3 Reliability of the Questionnaire

Reliability of the questionnaire alludes to its consistency. Inner consistency of a survey includes the reaction to everything of the poll with different things in the poll (Saunders et al, 2012). A regularly utilized measurement to quantify the inward consistency is Cronbach's Coefficient Alpha, which shows normal connection among the things of a scale. The worth extents from 0 to 1, higher worth shows more prominent dependability. In this exploration, the unwavering quality of two scales was estimated through Cronbach's Alpha as demonstrated as follows:

3.7.4 Reliability of the utilization of the web and the internet-based life scale

Table 5: Steadiness Statistics (6 items)

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	No. of Items
.882	6

3.7.5 Consistency of social media and politics scale

Table 6: Reliability Statistics (10 items)

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	No. of items
.943	10

The necessary degree of scale reliability is 0.70. The unwavering quality of scales utilized in this examination easily extends from 0.882 to 0.943. Subsequently, all the two scales are solid and inside reliable.

4. Data analysis and results

4.1 Quantitative analysis of research questions

One of the two examinations addresses targets recognizing what sort of preferences Social Media holds over the prevailing press and to search out how the Social Media is being and may make political mindfulness and activate fight developments in Pakistan. This is the most significant inquiry. The subsequent inquiry is whether the Social Media might be a helpful instrument for activists to make political mindfulness on political occasions and assemble political fights and shows in Pakistan. So as to locate an authentic and complete response to the greater part of the examination questions are given as follow:

Average internet use time per day

An attempt was made to identify the average internet use time in a day in Pakistan. A specific question was asked to the Facebook users. To answer this question, an interval scale was utilized as described in the questionnaire given at Appendix A.

The following table 4.1 indicates that more than 26% users of the internet use 0 – 3 hours, 32% use 4 – 6 hours, more than 28% use internet 7 – 9 hours, whereas only 13% users of the internet use 9 hours.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	0 – 3 hours	65	26.3	26.3	26.3
	4 – 6 hours	79	32.0	32.0	58.3
	7 – 9 hours	70	28.3	28.3	86.6
	More than 9 hours	33	13.4	13.4	100.0
	Total	247	100.0	100.0	

What does a social medium mean for you?

In response of the above-mentioned question the users of the Facebook responded that more than 25% users do social media for entertainment. More than 42% users do for communication with other people’s/ friends. Less than 16% utilize social media to share their views/ideas with each other while more than 16% users do social media for other purposes as shown in the following table.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Entertainment	63	25.5	25.5	25.5
	Communication	104	42.1	42.1	67.6
	Sharing	39	15.8	15.8	83.4
	Other	41	16.6	16.6	100.0

	Total	247	100.0	100.0	
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How frequently do you make use of social media applications?

Facebook

To observe the usage of Facebook on social media, a same three-point scale was used to get the responses from the Facebook users. It is mentioned in the following table 4.3 that more than 58% Facebook users often use Facebook. Less than 32% some time use Facebook. More than 10% never use Facebook. In this way majority of the respondents are 58% Facebook users.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Never	25	10.1	10.1	10.1
	Sometimes	78	31.6	31.6	41.7
	Often	144	58.3	58.3	100.0
	Total	247	100.0	100.0	

Do you accept that Social Media encourages you keep in contact with the individuals you don't find, in actuality, regularly?

An investigation of the table 10 uncovered that Social Media encourages you keep in contact with the individuals you don't find, all things considered, regularly. While gathering the reactions on this inquiry an ostensible scale (Yes, No) was utilized. Most of the respondents over 93% accept that Social Media helps keep in contact with individuals you don't find, in actuality, while over 6% don't accept on Social Media.

Table 10: Do you trust Social Media causes you keep in contact with the individuals you don't find, in actuality, frequently?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	231	93.5	93.5	93.5
	No	16	6.5	6.5	100.0
	Total	247	100.0	100.0	

Which of the statements beneath is characterizing you best about the sharing and updates via Social Media?

In this piece of the examination we survey a few articulations about sharing and updates via Social Media. About 34% of the respondents seek after the status of others as opposed to sharing and refreshing their own status. Fewer than 14% frequently offer and update their own status effectively. Over 40% reacted to sharing and following similarly while over 12% reacted not to share or tail others on the web-based life (see Table 12).

Table 11: Which of the statements beneath is characterizing you best about sharing and updates via Social Media?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	I follow others' updates and sharing	84	34.0	34.0	34.0
	I actively do sharing and update my status	34	13.8	13.8	47.8
	I do both equally	99	40.1	40.1	87.9
	I do not share and update my status on social media and do not follow others	30	12.1	12.1	100.0
	Total	247	100.0	100.0	

Whose sharing you follow on social media?

When the question asked from the social media users that who is sharing you most? More than 16% responded that they follow only their close friends or people I see often. Less than 79% were of the opinion that they follow all interesting posts while only more than 4% responded that they do not follow any post on social media as mentioned (see table 13).

Table 12: Whose sharing you follow on social media?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Only my close friends or people I see often.	41	16.6	16.6	16.6
	Any sharing that is interesting to me.	195	78.9	78.9	95.5
	I do not follow sharing on social media.	11	4.5	4.5	100.0
	Total	247	100.0	100.0	

Social media and politics

In this piece of study, the survey regarding the part of social media in politics was deliberated and various questions were asked to the participants and their responses are presented in the following sub sections:

Do you follow politics?

When the question asked do you follow politics to the users of the social media, fewer than 26% of the defendants responded that they follow actual politics. Less than 29% follow actual politics from time to time whereas more than 28% of the participants replied that they do not follow politics as shown in the table 14.

Table 13: Do you follow politics?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	64	25.9	25.9	25.9
	Sometimes	71	28.7	28.7	54.7
	No	112	45.3	45.3	100.0
	Total	247	100.0	100.0	

Which of the declarations underneath define you best on consuming social media for political purposes?

In response of the above question more than 6% of the social media users replied that they often do sharing on political subjects on social media. More than 9% stated that they only share political issues that are interesting to them. More than 18% responded that they do not share on politics, but they follow political sharing of others. More than 23% of the participants replied that they do not fill time on politics while using social media (see table 4.8).

Table 14: Which of the declarations underneath define you best on using social media for political purposes?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	I often do sharing with political subjects on social media.	28	6.6	11.3	11.3
	Even if not so often, I do sharing with political subjects which interest me.	41	9.7	16.6	27.9
	I do not do sharing with political subjects but I follow political sharing of others.	79	18.7	32.0	59.9
	I do not spend time for politics on social media.	99	23.5	40.1	100.0
	Total	247	58.5	100.0	

Do you forward a political sharing you liked on your own account?

When a question was asked regarding forwarding the sharing that they like more than 12% responded yes, more than 58% said sometimes, while more than 29% replied no as mentioned in the subsequent table 16.

Table 15: Do you forward a political sharing you liked on your own account?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	31	12.6	12.6	12.6
	Sometimes	144	58.3	58.3	70.9
	No	72	29.1	29.1	100.0
	Total	247	100.0	100.0	

Does a political sharing made via social media influence your thoughts or considerations regarding the matter?

In response of the above question more than 46% of the participants replied yes. The political sharing made on social media affects ones’ ideas or thoughts on the subject whereas less than 54% of the respondents replied that social media does not affect ones’ ideas or thoughts on the subject (see table 17).

Table 16: Does a political sharing made via social media influence your thoughts or considerations regarding the matter?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	114	46.2	46.2	46.2
	No	133	53.8	53.8	100.0
	Total	247	100.0	100.0	

Have you ever erased/obstructed a companion of yours as a result of his/her political sharing?

After an inspection of the following table 4.11 it is revealed that 20.6% of the people have either blocked or deleted their contacts on social media because of political sharing they made. The 79.4% respondents replied that they have neither blocked nor deleted their contacts on social media because of political sharing they made.

Table 17: Have you ever erased/obstructed a companion of yours as a result of his/her political sharing?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	51	20.6	20.6	20.6
	No	196	79.4	79.4	100.0
	Total	247	100.0	100.0	

Do you follow a policy-makers or a political activist through online media?

After an examination of the following table 19 it has been observed that 25.5% of the respondents follow a politician’s, a political group’s or an activist’s web page/ Face Book page on the social media. Majority of the respondents i.e. 74.5% of the respondents are not the followers of any politician, political group or activist on social media.

Table 18: Do you follow a policy-makers or a political activist through online media?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	63	25.5	25.5	25.5
	No	184	74.5	74.5	100.0
	Total	247	100.0	100.0	

Do you accept lawmakers utilize web-based media viably in Pakistan?

Only 9.7% of the respondents believe politicians use the social media effectively in Pakistan. About 10.5% do not believe whereas 79.8% of the respondents have no idea about the use of social media effectively by the Pakistani politicians (see table 20).

Table 19: Do you accept lawmakers utilize web-based media viably in Pakistan?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	24	9.7	9.7	9.7
	No	26	10.5	10.5	20.2
	I have no idea	197	79.8	79.8	100.0
	Total	247	100.0	100.0	

How much you agree with the statements below?

In the following six questions, a statement was given which was supposed to be answered by a five-point Likert scale (Strongly agree, Agree, Un-decided, Disagree and strongly disagree) was used to collect the data.

I sometime learn about political news from social media

As far as concerning the statement about learning political news from social media, 32% respondents were strongly agreed, 51% were agreed, 7.7% were neither agreed nor disagreed, and 7.7% were disagreed, while only 1.6% was strongly disagreed. Majority of the respondents showed their agreement with the statement as shown in the following table 21.

Table 20: Sometime I learn about political news from social media.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	79	32.0	32.0	32.0
	Agree	126	51.0	51.0	83.0
	Un-decided	19	7.7	7.7	90.7
	Disagree	19	7.7	7.7	98.4
	Strongly Disagree	4	1.6	1.6	100.0
	Total	247	100.0	100.0	

ii. I become familiar with some news via web-based media that were not transmission in the traditional press

An examination of the table 4.15 indicates that majority of the respondents i.e. 81% showed their agreement, while only 3.6% seemed to be disagreed whereas 15.4% participants

remained un-decided.

Table 21: I become familiar with some news via web-based media that were not transmission in the traditional press.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	66	26.7	26.7	26.7
	Agree	134	54.3	54.3	81.0
	Un-decided	38	15.4	15.4	96.4
	Disagree	6	2.4	2.4	98.8
	Strongly Disagree	3	1.2	1.2	100.0
	Total	247	100.0	100.0	

iii. I think conventional media is objectively free

In light of this inquiry, 56.6% of the respondents were seemed, by all accounts, to be unequivocally concurred or concurred with the announcement: "I accept that prevailing press is unbiased, goal and free". 32.4% respondents were remained un-chose while 10.9% demonstrated their conflict with the announcement (see table 23).

Table 22: I think conventional media is objectively free.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	43	17.4	17.4	17.4
	Agree	97	39.3	39.3	56.7
	Un-decided	80	32.4	32.4	89.1
	Disagree	21	8.5	8.5	97.6
	Strongly Disagree	6	2.4	2.4	100.0
	Total	247	100.0	100.0	

iv. I trust I got more news on social media than compared to mainstream media

In response to the statement: "I trust news I got social media more compared to mainstream media", the majority of 52.2% respondents appeared to be agreed, less than 32% respondents remained un-certain in their opinion whereas 15.8% participants showed their disagreement as shown in the table 24.

Table 23: I trust I got more news on social media than compared to mainstream media.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	38	15.4	15.4	15.4
	Agree	91	36.8	36.8	52.2
	Un-decided	79	32.0	32.0	84.2
	Disagree	33	13.4	13.4	97.6
	Strongly Disagree	6	2.4	2.4	100.0
	Total	247	100.0	100.0	

v. I think that social media is a powerful tool for communicating with people and creating responsiveness for political ideas

As far as the statement concerning “I believe that social media is a strong tool for reaching people and creating awareness for political purposes”, the majority of the respondents i.e. 85.9% seems to be in agreement, 11.7% remained un-decided, while only 2.4% respondents showed disagreement as indicated in the table 25.

Table 24: I think that social media is a powerful tool for communicating with people and creating responsiveness for political ideas.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid percent	Cumulative percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	117	47.4	47.4	47.4
	Agree	95	38.5	38.5	85.8
	Un-decided	29	11.7	11.7	97.6
	Disagree	4	1.6	1.6	99.2
	Strongly Disagree	2	.8	.8	100.0
Total		247	100.0	100.0	

Vi. I get knowledge regarding some political exhibitions, protests, or meetings through online media

Concerning about the statement that “I get informed of some political demonstrations, protests, or conferences through social media” majority of 70% respondents indicated agreement. More than 24% respondents were un-decided while less than 6% participants appeared to be disagreed with the statement as shown in table 26.

Table 25: I get knowledge regarding some political exhibitions, protests, or meetings through online media.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	84	34.0	34.0	34.0
	Agree	89	36.0	36.0	70.0
	Un-decided	60	24.3	24.3	94.3
	Disagree	9	3.6	3.6	98.0
	Strongly Disagree	5	2.0	2.0	100.0
Total		247	100.0	100.0	

Vii. Have you ever joined a political exhibition, dissent, or gathering that has been informed through social media?

Following table 27 indicates that only 12.1% have joined political demonstration, protest, or conference that has been informed about on social media. Majority of the respondents i.e. 87.9% have not joined the political conferences.

Table 26: Have you ever joined a political exhibition, dissent, or gathering that has been informed through social media?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	30	12.1	12.1	12.1
	No	217	87.9	87.9	100.0
	Total	247	100.0	100.0	

viii. Do you think political responses/reactions via online media are compelling strategies for political resistance?

The question about reactions/ criticisms on social media as effective methods of political opposition, 46.2% respondents believe that showing reaction or making criticism on social media is an effective way of making political opposition. The 25.9% respondents did not believe while 27.9% replied they have no idea as mentioned in the table 28.

Table 27: Do you think political responses/reactions via online media are compelling strategies for political resistance?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	114	46.2	46.2	46.2
	No	64	25.9	25.9	72.1
	I have no idea	69	27.9	27.9	100.0
	Total	247	100.0	100.0	

Analysing impact of social media on politics

By basic relapse investigation we survey the fluctuation in subordinate variable clarified by a free factor. The needy variable is legislative issues and free factor is Social Media. An examination of the accompanying table 4.22 uncovers the F-test 322.739 at p = 0.000 clarifies that model is factually solid. In the relapse model, estimation of R Square shows that fluctuation in the needy variable is clarified by the model. In this exploration, R square worth 0.568 is 56.8%. Henceforth, the model clarifies 56.8% fluctuation in subordinate variable. The relapse investigation shows that web-based social networking has critical effect on governmental issues.

Table 28: Model Summary

R	R Square	Std. Error of Estimate	F-value	Sig.
.754 ^a	.568	.28751	322.739	0.000
Standardized Coefficients				
Dependent variable	Independent variable	Beta	T-value	Sig.
Politics	Social Media	0.754	17.965	0.000

Analysing Impact of Facebook on Democracy

With respect to as the effect of Facebook on democracy is concern it is shown that F-Value 562.847 at p = 0.000 clarifies that model is factually solid. The R-Square worth shows the difference in the dependent variable clarified by the model. In the relapse model R-square worth 0.697 is 69.7%. The model clarifies 69.7% variance in dependent variable. The relapse investigation shows that Facebook has noteworthy effect of Facebook on popular government as appeared in the table31.

Table 29: Model Summary				
R	R Square	Std. Error of Estimate	F-value	Sig.
.835 ^a	.697	.45422	562.847	0.000
Standardized Coefficients				
Dependent variable	Independent variable	Beta	T-value	Sig.
Politics	Facebook	0.835	23.724	0.000

Testing of Hypotheses

In the Hypothesis 1, we anticipated that there is a positive effect of the utilization of Social Media on legislative issues. The speculation was tried by basic relapse technique. The outcomes demonstrated that R-Square worth clarified 56.8% fluctuation at essentialness esteem (p= 0.000). The Social Media has positive effect on the governmental issues of Pakistan in this manner the theory 1 has been acknowledged.

In the Hypothesis 2 we anticipated that there is a positive effect of Facebook on legislative issues. The speculation was tried by basic relapse. The outcome uncovered that R-Square worth clarified 69.7% difference at criticalness esteem (p= 0.000). This demonstrated Facebook has positive effect on governmental issues along these lines based on our discoveries the speculation 2 has been acknowledged.

5. Summary, Discussion, Conclusion, Findings, and Recommendations

This chapter is divided into five sections. Section one is about summary of the study, section two is related with discussion, section three is regarding to conclusions of the study, section four highlights on findings and finally section five is concerning with the recommendations.

5.1 Summary

This thesis has for the most part centred around the effect of Social Media on Politics. Its focal destinations have been to discover the effect of Social Media on Politics and the apparent effect of Facebook on Politics. As seen in checking on the writing, exact examinations which have been attempted on the utilization of web-based social network as an instrument for the advancement/improvement of democracy/politics as a general. While auditing the writing it was likewise seen that the hugeness of the job Facebook in foundation of Democracy in

Pakistan was recently disregarded yet later with the ubiquity of web in varying backgrounds, Politics couldn't stay unnoticed. Inside a time of the start of Social Media in Pakistan especially the Facebook gatherings and individual records, Pakistani legislative issues, popular government and Pakistani Politicians' exercises became significant issues of conversations on the Social Media stage in spite of enormous utilization of Facebook as a Social Media stage, there are shortage of writing in Pakistan on this territory, anyway much as has been done in the created nations. Subsequently the need was recognized for an experimental examination which centres around Facebook as instrument of Democracy on the grounds that Facebook is progressively well-known application when contrasted with other internet based life stages.

5.2 Discussion

1. The Hypothesis 1 was tried by straightforward relapse. Its outcomes indicated that R Square Value clarified 56.8% change at essentialness Value ($p= 0.000$), which implies the Social Media has positive effect on Politics of Pakistan. The Hypothesis 1 was acknowledged.
2. In the Hypothesis 2 (H2), it was anticipated that there was a positive effect of Facebook on Politics. This speculation was tried by straightforward relapse. The outcome uncovered that R Square worth clarified 69.7% change at noteworthiness esteem ($p= 0.000$). This showed Facebook positively affects governmental issues. The Hypothesis 2 was acknowledged.

Majority of the respondents strongly agreed that Facebook social media platform is significant to play a part to change society especially for the establishment of democracy in Pakistan. The level of interests among the higher educated persons in the urban areas is quite high due to internet facilities into the cities. This is also found that majority of the respondents are aspiring political knowledge from Facebook, thus it is certified that Facebook may influence the Pakistani people to political participation through social media platform Facebook so that they can decide on their own about voting behaviour or choice.

5.3 Conclusion

The absence of past efficient exploration here and the profoundly mind boggling multi-dimensional issues required inside every one of the fundamental factors has on occasion implied that issues might not have been examined adequately to arrive at resolutions. All things considered, many intriguing inquiries have been tended to and signs for additional exploration uncovered. The next might be viewed as the fundamental ends emerging from the present observational investigation. Overall, this study has created positive approach regarding the contribution of social media on political process in Pakistan. This study reveals that the users of the social media believe that they learn political news in a real sense from using the Facebook application of social media instead of mainstream media. As indicated by this study, Facebook plays an important role in proving and spreading information to the users in a proper manner on daily basis to the people who are spending more time for the use of Facebook. On this application of social media, the user's shares information to each other and this has created a chain for the receiving and sharing information to others.

1. This study also reveals that social media is more helpful for those people who don't meet

each other on daily basis due to the large distance. Hence, social media has reduced the distance among the people and created easy access to interact with each other.

2. The present study finds evidence in respect of learning political news from social media those were not broadcasted on mainstream media. It is also concluded that social media is more trustworthy than mainstream media.
3. It is also indicated that people get information regarding political demonstrations, protests or conferences through social media. It is obviously observed that social media is a strong tool for reaching people and creating awareness for political purposes.

5.4 Findings and Recommendations

In the light of the results following recommendations are put-forwarded for improving the use of social media to the users, who have keen interest in politics and are excited in receiving the political news.

1. The users of the Facebook believe that it provides latest information about political process of Pakistan. It is therefore, suggested that the social media application needs to be improved mostly in use of common people.
2. The results of this study reveal that Facebook is more used tool of social media through which people shares their information easily and effectively. It is recommended that maturity is required while using Facebook or any other application of social media because people of Pakistan are less educated and they share information to each other without its authenticity.
3. This study has provided evidence that social media has reduced the gap between the people they are not in easy access. It has been seriously noted that where social media is beneficiary for the people where social media has created lot of problems such as peoples mostly youngsters are more involved in use of social media and the ratio of users of social media users which are misusing the social media applications going to be increased. This increased ratio of misuses of social media by our youth is not good sign.
4. This study also proved that the social media provide more hidden information which mainstream media is not proving. This is the appreciable element of social media where print media and electronic media which follow the rules and regulations of Pakistan Electronic Media Regulatory Authority (PEMRA) remain silence to broadcast the news.
5. It is also observed that people get information regarding political demonstrations, protests or conferences through social media because of least coverage or no coverage on mainstream media. It is recommended that mainstream media may be given more freedom to broadcast the real news for the awareness of the peoples of Pakistan.

5.5 Implications of the Study

This study is an attempt to provide the knowledge to the researchers, academia and policy makers. The implication of first hypothesis is to find out the positive impact on politics, while the second hypothesis shows the importance of the Facebook pages relating to politics. The role of Facebook is expanding in the establishment of democracy in Pakistan as the popularity of Facebook and the public opinions discussed in this platform is increasing day by day. In a time when almost all of us are on Facebook, we need to ask how it's affecting the way that see ourselves, how we interact with others, and how we engage as citizens. Facebook innovated

an "architecture of disclosure" that is shaping the ways in which we think and act about politics. In view of this research is a timely effort and the results and recommendations concluded in this study would be beneficial to the concerned organizations working for the promotion of democracy in the country to obtain latest findings, the politicians themselves whose parties' websites are browsed by the Facebook members can judge their popularity and general opinions of the public about their political parties and overall political situation. This study can also be helpful for the future researchers.

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